

Appendix D

Refactoring Code Smells: Practical Guidelines

In this appendix, we provide a detailed explanation of how the removal of each of the 35 code smells for Elixir can be assisted by refactoring strategies (Chapter 5). Along with listing the refactorings useful for removing each smell and explaining their specific applications, we also document the order in which these refactorings should be performed when they are part of a sequence of operations. Specifically, when a refactoring should be used alone, it is listed with a bullet point (*i.e.*, •) in this appendix. Conversely, when a refactoring forms part of a sequence of operations, it is listed using numbering to define its order (*e.g.*, 1.; 2.; etc.)

This appendix is organized with a section for each code smell, arranged in alphabetical order. This document can **guide developers, especially those beginners to Elixir, on how to systematically remove code smells** and improve the internal quality of their systems implemented with this language.

D.1 Accessing non-existent map/struct fields

- **DEFAULT VALUE FOR AN ABSENT KEY IN A MAP:** When trying to access the value of a key from a `Map` dynamically, it is not possible to determine if a key is non-existent or if it has an associated `nil` value. This refactoring can eliminate the smell, as the ambiguity in the returns of dynamic accesses will no longer occur after its application.
- **INTRODUCE PATTERN MATCHING OVER A PARAMETER:** If the smell instance occurs in the function signature, such as in a guard clause, we can use this refactoring to extract the value of that field and then use it in the guard. This way, we can clearly determine if a field does not exist or if it simply has an associated `nil` value.

- **SIMPLIFYING CHECKS BY USING TRUTHNESS CONDITION:** Optionally, when using dynamic access to fields of a `Map` and needing to return a default value for non-existent fields or those associated with `nil`, we can perform this refactoring to solve this issue, thus producing cleaner code.
 - **EXPLICIT A DOUBLE BOOLEAN NEGATION:** Optionally, if we are using double boolean negation to check if a dynamically accessed field in a `Map` exists, this refactoring can improve code readability by replacing the unintuitive logic with helper functions that utilize pattern matching.
1. **STRUCT FIELD ACCESS ELIMINATION:** Optionally, if accesses to the same field, whether it exists or not, occur many times within a function, we can use this refactoring to replace these accesses with a temporary variable responsible for storing the value of that field.
 2. **EQUALITY GUARD TO PATTERN MATCHING:** Optionally, when a temporary variable extracted from a `struct` field is only used in an equality comparison in a guard, extracting and using that variable is unnecessary, as we can perform that equality comparison directly with pattern matching. To do this, we can use this refactoring.

D.2 Agent obsession

1. **GENERALISE A FUNCTION DEFINITION:** When functions responsible for directly interacting with the `Agent` are scattered throughout the system, it indicates the presence of this smell. We can refactor them simultaneously using this operation, centralizing the responsibility for interacting with the `Agent` in a single module or function.
2. **MOVING A DEFINITION:** After generalizing the functions that were originally responsible for directly accessing the `Agent`, the generic function created to centralize this task might not be located in the most appropriate module. This refactoring can be used to address this issue.
3. **ADD OR REMOVE A PARAMETER:** Functions that were originally responsible for directly accessing the `Agent`, once generalized by the previous refactoring, may require the addition of new parameters to be passed to the generic function called within their bodies.

- **BEHAVIOUR EXTRACTION:** One way to remove this smell is to define a **behaviour** containing a contract that specifies the format of all functions intended to interact with an **Agent** throughout the system. Following this refactoring, all modules that wish to access the **Agent** must implement this extracted **behaviour**.

D.3 Alternative return types

1. **INTRODUCE A TEMPORARY DUPLICATE DEFINITION:** When a function receives a **keyword list** as a parameter, which can drastically change its return type depending on its contents, we should initially use this refactoring to create a copy of the original function for each different return type.
2. **RENAME AN IDENTIFIER:** After creating the copies, we should rename each one according to its respective return type. Additionally, the bodies of the copies should be modified to fit the specific return types.
3. **EXPLICIT A CHANGED FUNCTION SIGNATURE (Composite)**
 - 3.1. **ADD OR REMOVE A PARAMETER:** At this point in the refactoring process, since the **keyword list** parameter is no longer necessary in any of the renamed copies of the original function, we can use this operation to remove the unnecessary parameter.
 - 3.2. **TYPING PARAMETERS AND RETURN VALUES:** Finally, we can use this operation on each of the functions involved in this composite refactoring to document their interfaces.
4. **REMOVE DEAD CODE:** This refactoring can be used on the copies of the functions created previously in this sequence of transformations to clean up their bodies, removing unused code.

D.4 Code organization by process

1. **REMOVE PROCESSES:** When code unnecessarily uses a process for organizational purposes where a simple module with functions would suffice, this refactoring can be

used to remove the unnecessary concurrent processes and replace them with regular Elixir modules.

2. REMOVE DEAD CODE: When we transform a process into a regular Elixir module, some functions that previously implemented process callbacks (*e.g.*, `GenServer`) may become unnecessary and can therefore be removed using this refactoring.

D.5 Comments

- EXTRACT FUNCTION: If a comment explains a block of code, that block can be extracted into a separate function. The name of the new function can often be derived from the comment itself.
- EXTRACT EXPRESSIONS: If a comment is intended to explain a complex expression, the expression should be split into understandable sub-expressions using this refactoring.
- EXTRACT CONSTANT: If a comment is used to explain magic numbers, this refactoring can replace the comments with constants that have human-friendly names.
- RENAME AN IDENTIFIER: If a function, expression, or constant has already been extracted, but comments are still necessary to explain what they do, give a self-explanatory name to them using this operation.
- TYPING PARAMETERS AND RETURN VALUES: If a comment is used to document the types of a function's parameters or the type of its return value, that comment can be replaced by a function specification using the `@spec` module attribute.
- ADD TYPE DECLARATIONS AND CONTRACTS: Alternatively, if a comment is used to document data structures received as parameters of a function or even returned by a function, this comment can be replaced by a type specification using the `@type` and `@typedoc` module attributes.

D.6 Compile-time global configuration

- **EXTRACT CONSTANT:** To remove this smell caused by using *Application Environment* in compile-time to define module's attributes (*i.e.*, constants), we can perform this refactoring in reverse, that is, perform an *inline* operation.
 - **INTRODUCE A TEMPORARY DUPLICATE DEFINITION:** We can also use this refactoring to create a copy of the compile-time defined constant and replace its definition with a call to `Application.compile_env/3` instead of `Application.fetch_env!/2`.
1. **FOLDING AGAINST A FUNCTION DEFINITION:** Another possibility would be to replace the location where a compile-time defined constant is used with a call to the *Application Environment* function responsible for defining the constant's content. This can be done using this refactoring.
 2. **REMOVE DEAD CODE:** Finally, if the compile-time defined constant is no longer used in the module, we can simply remove it.

D.7 Complex branching

- **EXTRACT FUNCTION:** When a function uses a conditional statement with many different branches, each responsible for handling a specific error type, we can use this refactoring to delegate each branch (*i.e.*, handling of a response type) to a different new private function. This approach makes the code cleaner, more concise, and readable.
- **INTRODUCE PATTERN MATCHING OVER A PARAMETER:** Another possibility is to use this refactoring to break down complex branching into a multi-clause function, where each clause handles a different error type. This approach enhances readability and maintainability by organizing the code according to distinct error scenarios.

D.8 Complex else clauses in with

1. **EXTRACT FUNCTION:** When an `else` clause in a `with` statement is used to handle different types of errors that may occur during the execution of the `with` clauses, the code can become confusing. To address this issue, we can use this refactoring to transform expressions in the `with` clauses into separate private functions. Each of these private functions will handle a specific error type, decentralizing the error-handling task.
 2. **REMOVE DEAD CODE:** After extracting the new functions responsible for decentralizing error handling, the `with` statement will no longer need an `else` clause. Therefore, we can use this refactoring to remove the `else` clause.
- **REMOVE REDUNDANT LAST CLAUSE IN "WITH":** Optionally, if the last clause of the `with` statement used to chain operations is redundant, we can use this refactoring to make the code less verbose and more readable.
 - **MOVING "WITH" CLAUSES WITHOUT PATTERN MATCHING:** Optionally, if the `with` statement does not perform pattern matching in the first and/or last clauses, we can use this refactoring to make the code more idiomatic and readable.

D.9 Complex extractions in clauses

- **SIMPLIFYING PATTERN MATCHING WITH NESTED STRUCTS:** When using pattern matching to perform deep extraction in nested `structs` passed as parameters to a clause of a multi-clause function, we may create unnecessarily messy and hard-to-understand code. With this refactoring, we can simplify this kind of extraction by performing pattern matching only on the outermost `struct` in the nesting, instead of matching patterns with very internal `structs`.
- **CONVERTS GUARDS TO CONDITIONALS:** To prevent complex extractions in clauses, which are used both to access data extracted in guard clauses and in the function body, from making the code confusing, we can use this refactoring to replace all guards with traditional conditionals, consolidating them into a single clause for the function. This way, all extracted data will be used exclusively in the function body.

- **EQUALITY GUARD TO PATTERN MATCHING:** Optionally, if an unnecessary temporary variable is extracted from a `struct`'s field in a clause of a multi-clause function and is only used for an equality comparison in a guard, this refactoring can simplify the pattern matching in that clause.
 - **STRUCT GUARD TO MATCHING:** Optionally, if some clauses of a multi-clause function use guard clauses involving the functions `is_struct/1` or `is_struct/2`, this refactoring can simplify the pattern matching performed by these clauses.
 - **REMOVE UNNECESSARY CALLS TO LENGTH/1:** If a list extraction is performed in a function clause only to use it in an unnecessary call to `length/1` in a guard clause, this extraction can be replaced by using pattern matching directly, eliminating the need for the guard clause. To do this, use this refactoring.
 - **FUNCTION CLAUSES TO/FROM CASE CLAUSES:** When complex extractions are done in clauses of multi-clause functions, making it difficult to understand which data is used inside or outside the function body, we can use this refactoring to transform a multi-clause function into a single clause function. By doing this, we will map the function's clauses into clauses of a `case` statement, ensuring that all extractions occur within the function body.
1. **INTRODUCE A TEMPORARY DUPLICATE DEFINITION:** When we are moving an extraction performed in a function clause into its body, we can initially use this refactoring to duplicate within the function body an extraction performed in the signature.
 2. **TEMPORARY VARIABLE ELIMINATION:** After duplicating the complex extraction within the function body, we can use this operation to remove unnecessary extracted parts, thereby cleaning up the code.

D.10 Data manipulation by Migration

1. **MODULE DECOMPOSITION (Composite)**
 - 1.1. **SPLITTING A LARGE MODULE:** When a module that behaves like `Ecto.Migration` performs both data and structural changes in a database schema, it becomes less cohesive, more difficult to test, and therefore more prone to bugs. In these cases, we should split this module into two, moving only the attributes and functions related to data updates to the new module.

- 1.2. **RENAME AN IDENTIFIER:** In some cases, after splitting an original module into several smaller and more cohesive modules, the name of the original module can no longer make sense, providing an opportunity also to perform this refactoring.
2. **EXTRACT TO OUTSIDE (Composite)**
 - 2.1. **EXTRACT FUNCTION:** We can use this operation in the original module to create a new function responsible for calling the routines for altering the data in the database, now present in the new module.
 - 2.2. **MOVING A DEFINITION:** After extracting this function, we can use this refactoring to reposition it in the new module created after splitting the original module.
3. **REMOVE DEAD CODE:** Finally, we can eliminate the call to the extracted function in the original module to start the database alteration routines, as this function, now present in the new module, should only be called during the initialization of a `Mix.Task`.
- **SIMPLIFYING ECTO SCHEMA FIELDS VALIDATION:** Optionally, we can take the opportunity to apply this refactoring in the original module, making it less prone to errors during the validation of the database schema modified via `Ecto.Migration`.
- **PIPELINE FOR DATABASE TRANSACTIONS:** Optionally, we can also take the opportunity to apply this operation in the new module created only to perform changes on data, thus improving its readability by using `Ecto.Multi`.

D.11 Divergent change

- **MODULE DECOMPOSITION (Composite)**
 1. **SPLITTING A LARGE MODULE:** This smell can be removed by creating new cohesive modules and moving related functions into them.
 2. **RENAME AN IDENTIFIER:** In some cases, after splitting an original module into several smaller and more cohesive modules, the name of the original module can no longer make sense, providing an opportunity to also apply this refactoring.
- **MOVING A DEFINITION:** If there is already a module `B` that is more suitable to accommodate a function that makes module `A` less cohesive, we can simply move this function from module `A` to module `B` to remove this smell.

- **BEHAVIOUR EXTRACTION:** This smell can be removed by creating a new cohesive module **B** and moving related functions of module **A** into it. Thereby, we can use this refactoring to transform module **A** into a *behaviour definition* and create module **B** as a *behaviour implementation* of module **A**, thus achieving this goal.

D.12 Duplicated code

- **DEFINING A SUBSET OF A MAP:** It can be used to eliminate duplicated code generated by the manual access of values when extracting part of a `Map`.
- **MODIFYING KEYS IN A MAP:** This refactoring can be used to eliminate duplicated code generated by the manual process of replacing a name given to a `Map` key.
- **FOLDING AGAINST A FUNCTION DEFINITION:** When code contains expressions that perform operations already implemented in existing functions, we can remove this code duplication by using this refactoring, thus replacing the own expressions with calls to the existing functions.
- **EXTRACT EXPRESSIONS:** When the same expression is repeated multiple times within a function, we can assign the expression to a variable and reuse that variable in all parts where the result of the expression is needed.
- **EXTRACT FUNCTION:** When the same code block appears in two different functions, we can extract it to a new function and call this function from both places where the code was originally duplicated.
- **REDUCING A BOOLEAN EQUALITY EXPRESSION:** When dealing with a boolean expression consisting of multiple equality comparisons involving the same variable and logical `OR` operators, we can eliminate duplicated code using this refactoring, thus utilizing the `IN` operator and a list containing all possible valid values for the variable.
- **GENERALISE A FUNCTION DEFINITION:** When we have different functions that have non-identical but equivalent expressions, we can use this refactoring to create a new higher-order function that generalizes the equivalent expressions and subsequently is called in places where the expressions were originally used.
- **TURNING ANONYMOUS INTO LOCAL FUNCTIONS:** When we encounter the same anonymous function being defined in different points of the codebase, these anonymous functions should be transformed into a local function, and the locations where

the anonymous functions were originally implemented should be updated to use the new local function.

- **MERGING MULTIPLE DEFINITIONS:** There are situations where a codebase may have distinct and complementary functions. Because they are complementary, these functions may have identical code snippets. When identified, these functions can be merged into a new function that will simultaneously perform the processing done by the original functions separately.
 - **MOVE EXPRESSION OUT OF CASE:** When the same expression is repeated at the end of all branches of a `case` statement, this refactoring can be used to eliminate the duplicated code.
 - **REMOVE REDUNDANT LAST CLAUSE IN "WITH":** When the last clause of a `with` statement is composed of a pattern identical to the predefined value to be returned by the `with` in case all checked patterns match, this clause is considered redundant. Therefore this duplicated code can be eliminated using this refactoring.
 - **STATIC STRUCTURE REUSE:** When identical `tuples` or `lists` are used at different points within a function, they are unnecessarily recreated by Elixir. Use this refactoring to eliminate these redundant recreations by assigning the structures to variables, allowing them to be shared throughout the code.
 - **INTRODUCE IMPORT:** When a module `A` calls many functions from a module `B`, the name of module `B` may appear repetitively in the code of module `A` due to fully-qualified name calls. This type of duplicated code can be eliminated by importing module `B` into module `A`.
 - **WIDEN OR NARROW DEFINITION SCOPE:** When we encounter the same anonymous function defined in different parts of the codebase, these functions should be transformed into a local function, eliminating code duplication by expanding the scope of the original function. This refactoring serves as an alternative to **TURNING ANONYMOUS INTO LOCAL FUNCTIONS**.
1. **INTRODUCE `Enum.map/2`:** When each element of a `list` is manually generated by repeatedly calling the same function, we can use this refactoring to eliminate duplicated code and make the code more idiomatic.
 2. **TRANSFORM TO LIST COMPREHENSION:** Optionally, after using the previous refactoring to eliminate duplicated code, we can use this operation to convert the call to `Enum.map/2` into semantically equivalent code that can be also more declarative and easier to read.

3. LIST COMPREHENSION SIMPLIFICATIONS: Optionally, after using the previous refactoring as part of a sequence of atomic refactorings to eliminate duplicated code, we can also use this refactoring to revert the previous transformation, thereby retaining calls to the higher-order function `Enum.map/2` instead of using list comprehensions.

D.13 Dynamic atom creation

1. EXTRACT FUNCTION: We can replace a call to the function `String.to_atom/1` with an explicit conversion. To do this, we can use this refactoring on the calls to `String.to_atom/1`, creating a new function. This new function should take a `string` as a parameter and convert it to an `atom`. The body of this function should include a conditional to check the content of the `string`. Depending on its content, the function will return a different `atom` directly.
2. INTRODUCE PATTERN MATCHING OVER A PARAMETER: After extracting a new function for explicit conversions from `strings` to `atoms`, we can use this refactoring to transform the function into a multi-clause function, where each clause is responsible for returning one of the possible converted `atoms`.
 - FOLDING AGAINST A FUNCTION DEFINITION: If there is already a function in the module responsible for performing the explicit conversion of a `string` to an `atom` (*e.g.*, a function extracted for this purpose at a different point in the same module), we can replace a call to `String.to_atom/1` with a call to that function.
 - GRADUAL CHANGE (Composite)
 1. INTRODUCE A TEMPORARY DUPLICATE DEFINITION: Another alternative to refactor this code is to first duplicate the line where the function `String.to_atom/1` is called to create an `atom` dynamically. The new line should replace the call to `String.to_atom/1` with a call to `String.to_existing_atom/1`. This will ensure that `string-to-atom` conversions only map the `strings` to `atoms` already in memory. To enable this type of mapping, a suggestion is to create a `list` of these possible `atoms` within the function where this refactoring was applied.
 2. REMOVE DEAD CODE: After duplicating and modifying the duplicated line, we can eliminate the original line where the call to `String.to_atom/1` occurred.

D.14 Feature envy

- EXTRACT TO OUTSIDE (Composite)
 1. EXTRACT FUNCTION: If part of a function calls more functions from other modules than from the module where it is defined, we can use this refactoring to separate the envious part into a new function.
 2. MOVING A DEFINITION: If a function calls more functions from other modules than from the module where it is defined (*e.g.*, the function extracted in the previous refactoring), we can move it to the module most accessed by it.
- REMOVE IMPORT ATTRIBUTES: By using this refactoring, we can directly identify the origin of a function being called by another function. This way, we can more clearly identify a FEATURE ENVY instance, helping us to subsequently remove it.

D.15 GenServer envy

1. GENERALISE A PROCESS ABSTRACTION: When an `Agent` or `Task` goes beyond its suggested use cases and becomes painful, it is better to refactor it into a `GenServer` using this operation.
2. INTRODUCE PROCESSES: When we finish generalizing a process, it may still be insufficient to achieve an optimal mapping with the parallel activities of the problem being solved. In these circumstances, we can use this refactoring to remove bottlenecks.
3. REGISTER A PROCESS: When we create a new process, we can also use this refactoring to assign a user-defined name to the new process ID and use that user-defined name instead of the process ID in message passing.
4. REMOVE DEAD CODE: When we are generalizing a process `Agent` or `Task` into a `GenServer`, naturally, some functions of the module that represented the original process may become useless and can therefore be removed.

D.16 Inappropriate intimacy

1. **CLOSURE CONVERSION:** A specific type of **INAPPROPRIATE INTIMACY** can be seen in closures, which are impure anonymous functions, as they access variables outside their scope. One way to remove this smell is by transforming the closure into a pure anonymous function.
 2. **ADD OR REMOVE A PARAMETER:** Imagine the scenario where an anonymous function **A** is defined within a named function **B**. Furthermore, consider that **A** accesses a variable in its body that is a parameter of **B**, which is not passed as a parameter to **A** (*i.e.*, function **A** is a closure). When applying the previous refactoring to remove the **INAPPROPRIATE INTIMACY** instance in **A**, we may end up with unused parameters in the named function **B**. Therefore, we can use the present refactoring in **B** to fix it.
- **MOVING A DEFINITION:** If a function in module **A** is impure because it accesses internal details of module **B** without receiving them through its parameters, we can remove this smell by moving the function from **A** to **B**, thus reducing the coupling between modules.
 - **MODULE DECOMPOSITION (Composite)**
 1. **SPLITTING A LARGE MODULE:** If the modules involved in an instance of this smell have common interests, we can use this refactoring to put their commonality in a new module and make them high-cohesive and low-coupling modules.
 2. **RENAME AN IDENTIFIER:** In some cases, after splitting an original module into several smaller and more cohesive modules, the name of the original module can no longer make sense, providing an opportunity to also apply this refactoring.

D.17 Large class

- **MODULE DECOMPOSITION (Composite)**
 1. **SPLITTING A LARGE MODULE:** When a module does the work of two or more, it becomes large, poorly cohesive, and difficult to maintain. In these cases, we should split this module into several new ones, moving to each new module only the attributes and functions with purposes related to their respective goals.

2. **RENAME AN IDENTIFIER:** In some cases, after splitting an original module into several smaller and more cohesive modules, the name of the original module can no longer make sense, providing an opportunity to also apply this refactoring.
- **BEHAVIOUR EXTRACTION:** This operation is helpful if it's necessary to have a list of operations and behaviors that client modules can reuse, thus reducing their sizes.
 - **MOVING A DEFINITION:** When a function is defined in module **A** but is more suited to the responsibilities of module **B**, we can move it to **B** to reduce the size of **A**.

D.18 Large code generation by macros

- **EXTRACT TO OUTSIDE (Composite)**
 1. **EXTRACT FUNCTION:** When we have a `macro` that generates a large volume of code, potentially compromising compiler performance, we can use this refactoring to extract part of the `macro`'s code and encapsulate it in a conventional function that the `macro` will call. This approach reduces the amount of code that is expanded and compiled with each invocation of the `macro`.
 2. **MOVING A DEFINITION:** After extracting the function, it may eventually be necessary to move it to another module to make the code more cohesive.

D.19 Large messages

- **DEFINING A SUBSET OF A MAP:** If we are originally sending a complete `Map` from one process to another, but actually only need to send a few fields from this `Map`, we can use this refactoring to help reduce the size of the message sent.
- **EXTRACT EXPRESSIONS:** When we use `spawn/1` to perform message passing between processes, we can pass an anonymous function as a parameter to `spawn/1` that accesses a `Map` field in its body. This will still copy over all of the `Map`, because the `Map` variable is being captured inside the spawned function. The function then extracts the field, but only after the whole `Map` has been copied over. Suppose we only need to send one field of a `Map` between processes. In that case, we can reduce the size of this

message by using this refactoring to store only the necessary value of the `Map` field in a temporary variable. This variable is then used in the spawned function.

- **ADD A TAG TO MESSAGES:** Optionally, when we are removing this code smell, we may have the opportunity to adapt the processes that communicate with each other by adding tags that identify groups of messages exchanged between them.

D.20 Long function

- **EXTRACT FUNCTION:** If a comment is needed to explain some part of the function body, this refactoring can be used to create a new function to be called at the location of this comment, thus decreasing the size of the original function.
- **TRANSFORM NESTED "IF" STATEMENTS INTO A "COND":** If a function uses many nested `if` conditionals, this can greatly increase its size. In these cases, we can use this refactoring to decrease the size of the function.
- **FOLDING AGAINST A FUNCTION DEFINITION:** If a function performs operations that can be delegated to other existing functions, it may become unnecessarily long. In these cases, we can use this refactoring to reduce the size of the original function.
- **REMOVE DEAD CODE:** If a function contains code that is no longer used, it may become unnecessarily long. In these cases we can use this refactoring to reduce the size of the original function.
- **SIMPLIFYING CHECKS BY USING TRUTHNESS CONDITION:** When we know that a given data item can be `nil` and we need to return a default value if it is indeed `nil`, we can use this refactoring to reduce the number of lines in a function while maintaining clean and self-explanatory code.
- **GENERALISE A FUNCTION DEFINITION:** When different functions have equivalent expression structures, these equivalent expressions can be generalized into a new higher-order function, thus reducing the size of the original functions.
- **INTRODUCE PATTERN MATCHING OVER A PARAMETER:** When a function has many branches in its body that depend on values received as parameters, it can become unnecessarily long. We can use this refactoring to create short multi-clauses for the original function, where each clause handles a different branch.

- REPLACE PIPELINE WITH A FUNCTION: When a function is unnecessarily long due to a pipeline of function calls that can be replaced by a single call, we can use this refactoring to address the issue.
 - DEFAULT VALUE FOR AN ABSENT KEY IN A MAP: A function can have its number of lines reduced by using this refactoring to replace the use of `if` statements that check the return of `Map.has_key?/2` with a call to the `Map.get/3` function.
 - DEFINING A SUBSET OF A MAP: When a function is unnecessarily long because it manually creates a subset of a `Map` by individually accessing each of the desired key/-value pairs, we can use this refactoring to delegate this task to a call to `Map.take/2`.
 - PIPELINE USING "WITH": When a function uses nested conditionals solely to control a sequence of function calls, it can become long. By using this refactoring, we can make the function more idiomatic and reduce its number of lines of code.
 - REMOVE REDUNDANT LAST CLAUSE IN "WITH": This refactoring can reduce the number of lines of code used by a `with` statement and consequently shorten the size of the function that uses this statement.
 - MODIFYING KEYS IN A MAP: When a function is unnecessarily long because it manually replaces a `Map` key with a new key using `Map.get/2`, `Map.put/2`, and `Map.delete/2` functions together, we can use this refactoring to delegate this task to a call to `Map.new/2`, thus significantly reducing the volume of lines of code.
 - REMOVE NESTED CONDITIONAL STATEMENTS IN FUNCTION CALLS: When a function uses unnecessary nested conditional statements, it can become long and less readable. In such circumstances, we can use this refactoring to replace the unnecessary nested conditional statements with less bulky code that maintains the same behavior, thus making the code simpler and more readable.
 - SPLITTING A DEFINITION: When the refactoring MERGING MULTIPLE DEFINITIONS is used carelessly, there is a risk of creating a long function. In such cases, we can undo this operation using the present refactoring, thereby generating smaller, separate functions.
 - MERGING MATCH EXPRESSIONS INTO A LIST PATTERN: If a function uses many lines of code with expressions that assign results to temporary variables but can be replaced by a single `list` generated through pattern matching, we can use this refactoring to reduce the size of the function.
1. CONVERT NESTED CONDITIONALS TO PIPELINE: When a function uses nested conditionals solely to control a sequence of function calls, it can become long. By

using this refactoring, we can give the function a more functional appearance and reduce the number of lines of code.

2. REPLACE FUNCTION CALL WITH RAW VALUE IN A PIPELINE START: When using the previous refactoring to remove this smell, we may also encounter an opportunity to apply the present operation, making the refactored code more idiomatic.

D.21 Long parameter list

- ADD OR REMOVE A PARAMETER: If a function parameter for some reason is never used, it can be removed using this refactoring.
- REORDER PARAMETER: When a function has a long list of parameters that reduces its readability, we can at least reorder the list into a more logical sequence to improve clarity.
- INTRODUCE PARAMETER STRUCT (Composite)
 1. GROUPING PARAMETERS IN TUPLE: If a function has sequential and related parameters in its list, these parameters can be grouped into a tuple, thus reducing the length of the list.
 2. FROM TUPLE TO STRUCT: A tuple used to group parameters can eventually be replaced by a struct using this refactoring.

D.22 Modules with identical names

- RENAME AN IDENTIFIER: In Elixir, there is a naming convention for modules that should be followed when implementing libraries. According to this convention, a library should use its own name as a prefix (namespace) for all its module names (*e.g.*, `LibraryName.ModuleName`). When a library does not adhere to this naming convention, it can lead to name conflicts for the library's clients. To remove this smell, we can rename the modules of a library to adapt them to this convention. It is important to be careful when performing this refactoring on already released libraries, as it may cause breaking changes in client code.

- GRADUAL CHANGE (Composite)
 1. INTRODUCE A TEMPORARY DUPLICATE DEFINITION: As explained in the previous refactoring, when a library does not follow the naming convention for modules, it can lead to name conflicts in their clients. To remove this smell in already released libraries, we can use this present refactoring on the modules of a library, adapting the names of the copies to this convention. Meanwhile, the modules with names outside the convention should be marked as deprecated but not immediately removed, to avoid breaking client code.
 2. REMOVE DEAD CODE: When modules deprecated by the previous refactoring have remained deprecated long enough for clients to adapt to the new naming conventions, we can use this refactoring to permanently eliminate them, thereby removing the risk of name conflicts.
- MOVE FILE: If the same directory contains two modules with the same name defined in different files, we can use this refactoring to relocate one of these modules to a new directory. Naturally, we will also need to rename the moved module to conform to the naming convention for modules in Elixir, which recommends using the directory name as a prefix (namespace) for all module names contained within it (*e.g.*, `LibraryName.ModuleName`).

D.23 Primitive obsession

- INTRODUCE PARAMETER STRUCT (Composite)
 1. GROUPING PARAMETERS IN TUPLE: If primitive/basic type values are used in function parameters to inadequately represent more complex real-world abstractions, you can initially apply this refactoring to group them.
 2. FROM TUPLE TO STRUCT: A `tuple` used to group parameters can eventually be replaced by a `struct`, thus creating a more robust data structure for this purpose.
- ADD TYPE DECLARATIONS AND CONTRACTS: We can use this refactoring to generate a type specification to replace primitive/basic values.

D.24 Shotgun surgery

- **MOVING A DEFINITION:** When we need to simultaneously make a series of small changes in different modules, it's easy to overlook something important. In this case, you can use this refactoring to reorganize the modules, aiming to make them more cohesive so that all necessary changes are concentrated within their respective modules. If no current module seems like a good candidate to receive parts moved from others, we need to create one.

D.25 Speculative assumptions

- **INTRODUCE PATTERN MATCHING OVER A PARAMETER:** This smell arises when developers write defensive or imprecise code, which can return incorrect values that were not planned for. To remove it, we can use this refactoring to force a function to crash instead of returning an invalid value when something unexpected happens.
- **PIPELINE USING "WITH":** If this smell occurs within nested conditional statements, we can use this refactoring to remove them. This operation relies on pattern matching to prevent the continuation of tasks that depend on specific data formats.

D.26 Speculative generality

- **INLINE FUNCTION:** Use this refactoring to get rid of unused functions or even unnecessarily created ones.
- **INLINE MACRO:** Similarly to the previous refactoring, use this operation to eliminate unused macros or those that were unnecessarily created.
- **ADD OR REMOVE A PARAMETER:** Functions with unused parameters should be reviewed using this refactoring.
- **RENAME AN IDENTIFIER:** Functions with abstract names should be renamed using more specific names that reflect their current task, rather than potential future tasks

they might perform.

- **BEHAVIOUR INLINING:** Unnecessary delegation/generalization caused by the excessive use of Elixir’s `behaviour` can be removed with this refactoring.
- **REMOVE DEAD CODE:** In general, any code created unnecessarily to support future features that are never implemented can be refactored using this operation.
- **ELIMINATE SINGLE BRANCH:** When a conditional is created to potentially provide different treatments for different types of data but actually provides the same treatment to all, we can simplify the code by removing unnecessary complexity.

D.27 Switch statements

1. **REPLACE CONDITIONAL WITH POLYMORPHISM VIA PROTOCOLS:** Suppose the same sequence of conditional statements appears duplicated in the code. In that case, we may be forced to make changes in multiple parts of the code whenever a new check needs to be added to these duplicated sequences of conditional statements. This refactoring introduces polymorphism to data structures, thus improving the code’s extensibility to handle flow controls based on data types.
2. **CONVERTS GUARDS TO CONDITIONALS:** The inverse operation of this present refactoring can be used to complement the previous refactoring operation, combining polymorphism with guard clauses in the implementation of the functions defined in the created `Protocol`.
 - **INTRODUCE PATTERN MATCHING OVER A PARAMETER:** If a switch/conditional of a function is based on a set of numbers or strings that form a list of allowable values for some parameter (*i.e.*, “type code”), we can use this refactoring to replace the conditional with a multi-clause function.
 - **INTRODUCE OVERLOADING:** We can overload a function, transforming it into a multi-clause function, to eliminate a conditional.
1. **EXTRACT TO OUTSIDE (Composite)**
 - 1.1. **EXTRACT FUNCTION:** Often the duplicated switch/conditional statement switches on a “type code”. To isolate a switch/conditional in a *type code host*, start by extracting one of the duplicated switch/conditional statements into a new function.

- 1.2. MOVING A DEFINITION: Second, the extracted function should be moved to the right module.
2. GENERALISE A FUNCTION DEFINITION: After the previous composite refactoring, the moved function should be transformed into a higher-order function. One of the parameters of this generalized function will receive a function as an argument, responsible for defining the strategy of the internal conditional check.
3. FOLDING AGAINST A FUNCTION DEFINITION: Finally, all points in the code with duplicated switch/conditional statements can use this refactoring to replace the duplicated code with calls to the previously defined higher-order function.

D.28 Unnecessary macros

- **INLINE MACRO:** When code is implemented as a `macro` but could be implemented as a conventional function in Elixir, we can use this refactoring to remove this smell, improving the readability of the code.
- **EXTRACT TO OUTSIDE (Composite)**
 1. **EXTRACT FUNCTION:** When creating a `macro` is unavoidable, but part of it could be implemented as a conventional named function, we can extract this part of the `macro`'s code and encapsulate it into a conventional function, which the `macro` will then call. This approach improves code organization and readability while leveraging the `macro` for its specific role.
 2. **MOVING A DEFINITION:** After extracting the function, it may eventually be necessary to move it to another module to make the code more cohesive.

D.29 Unrelated multi-clause function

1. **RENAME AN IDENTIFIER:** A possible solution to this smell is to use this refactoring to break up the business rules that are mixed into several different simple functions. Specifically, groups of clauses from the original function that share related func-

tionalties can be renamed with an identical name, thus forming a new multi-clause function.

2. **FUNCTION CLAUSES TO/FROM CASE CLAUSES:** Optionally, after renaming the groups of related clauses, thus creating new multi-clause functions, these multi-clause functions can be transformed into single-clause functions by mapping function clauses into clauses of `case` statements.
- **MOVING A DEFINITION:** When unrelated clauses of a multi-clause function differ to the point where they do not make sense in the current module, these clauses can be moved to other modules where they fit better, thus making the code more cohesive.
 - **STRUCT GUARD TO MATCHING:** Optionally, when some of the clauses of a multi-clause function use a guard clause involving the functions `is_struct/1` or `is_struct/2`, we can use this refactoring to simplify the pattern matching performed by these function clause's signature.
 - **EQUALITY GUARD TO PATTERN MATCHING:** Optionally, when an unnecessary temporary variable is extracted from a `struct`'s field in a clause of a multi-clause function only to be used in an equality comparison in a guard, we can use this operation to simplify the pattern matching performed by this function clause's signature.
 - **SIMPLIFYING GUARD SEQUENCES:** Optionally, when a clause of a multi-clause function contains redundant logical propositions, we can simplify the pattern matching performed by this function clause's signature through the transformation carried out by this refactoring.
 - **CONVERTS GUARDS TO CONDITIONALS:** Optionally, when what differentiates the clauses of a multi-clause function are only the logical checks performed in their guard clauses, we can use this refactoring to replace all guards with traditional conditionals, creating only one clause for the function.
 - **SIMPLIFYING PATTERN MATCHING WITH NESTED STRUCTS:** Optionally, when using pattern matching to perform deep extraction in nested `structs` passed as parameters to a clause of a multi-clause function, we may create unnecessarily messy and hard-to-understand code. With this refactoring, we can simplify this kind of extraction by performing pattern matching only on the outermost `struct` in the nesting, instead of matching patterns with very internal `structs`.
 - **REMOVE UNNECESSARY CALLS TO LENGTH/1:** Optionally, when unnecessary calls to the function `length/1` are used in guard clauses to differentiate the pattern matching performed by different clauses of a multi-clause function, we can replace these

calls with direct pattern matching on the parameter list of the function clauses, thereby improving code efficiency.

D.30 Unsupervised process

- **MOVING ERROR-HANDLING MECHANISMS TO SUPERVISION TREES:** Regardless of whether error-handling mechanisms are used or not, an unsupervised process can be moved to a supervision tree using this refactoring. With this transformation, the initialization of processes is delegated to a `Supervisor` and is no longer performed directly by the clients. This refactoring allows you to choose which module that behaves as a `Supervisor` to move to, or even to create a new module that implements the `Application` behaviour to act as a supervision tree.
- **MOVING A DEFINITION:** We can move the process initialization function calls (*e.g.*, `GenServer.start/3`) into a `Supervisor`, delegating this task to it.

D.31 Untested polymorphic behaviors

1. **INTRODUCE OVERLOADING:** We can use this refactoring to transform a simple polymorphic function into a multi-clause function, where each clause of the function is responsible for handling one of the supported data types.
 2. **FOLDING AGAINST A FUNCTION DEFINITION:** After transforming a polymorphic function into a multi-clause function, we can use this refactoring to delegate part of the processing within a clause's body to calls of other clauses of the same function.
- **TYPING PARAMETERS AND RETURN VALUES:** Another improvement possibility for code suffering from this code smell is to use this refactoring to document a polymorphic function, making it clear which data types it supports.

D.32 "Use" instead of "import"

1. **INTRODUCE IMPORT:** When a `use` directive is unnecessarily used to establish a dependency between two modules, it can lead to unwanted propagation of internal dependencies from module `A` to module `B`. To remove this smell, we can initially replace a `use` directive with an `import` or `alias` directive. For this, we can first use this refactoring, which will create a more superficial dependency in module `B` with module `A`.
2. **REMOVE DEAD CODE:** After adding the `import` directive, we should remove the `use` directive using this refactoring.
 - **ALIAS EXPANSION:** Optionally, if the directive used to replace `use` is an `alias` and it is in the multi-alias format (*e.g.*, `alias Foo.Bar.{Baz, Boom}`), we can use this refactoring, thus providing an improvement in code readability and traceability.
 - **REMOVE IMPORT ATTRIBUTES:** Optionally, if after replacing `use` with `import` we identify that a module is excessively importing other modules to the point of impairing readability—making it difficult to identify the origin of the functions it calls—we can perform this refactoring to some unnecessary imports. After that, we will then call the functions from the removed `imports` by their fully-qualified names.

D.33 Using App Configuration for libraries

- **EXPLICIT A CHANGED FUNCTION SIGNATURE (Composite)**
 1. **ADD OR REMOVE A PARAMETER:** When we have a library function that depends on globally defined values, which reduces its reusability, we can use this refactoring to add a new optional parameter of type `Keyword list` with a default value. This new parameter allows the function to be configured in different ways when called. If the optional parameter is not provided in the call, the function will continue to behave as originally, using the same global configurations.
 2. **TYPING PARAMETERS AND RETURN VALUES:** We can also use this refactoring to explicitly document the type of the added parameter (*i.e.*, `Keyword list`).

D.34 Using exceptions for control-flow

1. **RENAME AN IDENTIFIER:** To prevent a library function from always forcing third-party code to handle an error as an exception, we can initially rename the original function, adding a trailing `!` at the end of its name. In Elixir, there is a convention where a `!` (*i.e.*, *trailing* or *bang*) at the end of a function name indicates that it may raise an exception.
 2. **INTRODUCE A TEMPORARY DUPLICATE DEFINITION:** After renaming the original function by adding a `!` at the end of its name, we can use this refactoring to duplicate the renamed original function. This copy should have the original function's name, without the `!` at the end. Instead of raising exceptions, it should return data in the `tuple` format (*i.e.*, `{:ok, _}` or `{:error, msg}`). The message provided in the error `tuple` should be the same as the one originally displayed in the exception version.
 3. **FOLDING AGAINST A FUNCTION DEFINITION:** Finally, we can use the present refactoring to change the *bang* variant (*i.e.*, the original function that raises an exception, with `!` at the end of its name). With this transformation, the raising version is implemented on top of the non-raising version of the code.
1. **INTRODUCE PROCESSES:** Another possibility for removing this smell is, if the module where the function that raises an exception is not a process (*e.g.*, `GenServer` or `Task`), we can use this refactoring to transform the module into a process.
 2. **MOVING ERROR-HANDLING MECHANISMS TO SUPERVISION TREES:** When a process is using defensive programming (*i.e.*, `try..rescue`) to handle exceptions and even control the execution flow, we can use this refactoring to eliminate this type of handling, transitioning instead to the *"Let it crash"* style.

D.35 Working with invalid data

1. **TYPING PARAMETERS AND RETURN VALUES:** When a library function does not validate the types of its parameters at its signature, we can at least use this refactoring to document these data. This will help the clients of this function (*i.e.*, third-party code) to protect themselves from potential errors caused by invalid data.

2. **ADD TYPE DECLARATIONS AND CONTRACTS:** If recurring data structures are found when documenting functions of a library, these structures can be named using the present refactoring, thus creating new reusable data types and increasing the system's readability.
- **INTRODUCE PATTERN MATCHING OVER A PARAMETER:** Optionally, if a client validates the data passed to a library function call using traditional conditional statements, we can use this refactoring to make the client function more idiomatic while still addressing the smell.
- **STRUCT GUARD TO MATCHING:** Optionally, if a guard clause involving the functions `is_struct/1` or `is_struct/2` is used to avoid working with invalid data, we can use this refactoring to simplify the code used to remove this code smell.
- **SIMPLIFYING GUARD SEQUENCES:** Optionally, if a guard clause with redundancies is used to avoid working with invalid data, we can use the present refactoring to also simplify the code used to remove this code smell.
- **CONVERTS GUARDS TO CONDITIONALS:** Optionally, we can replace guard clauses used in a multi-clause client function to handle invalid data with traditional conditional statements. By doing so, we can use this refactoring to consolidate all data type validations into a single-clause function.